

SPORT DISCOURSE AS A TYPE OF FUNCTIONAL STYLE

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Abstract:

The history of boxing goes back more than a thousand years. In Egypt (paintings on frescoes), as well as in Minoan and Sumerian reliefs, there are various references to fists. According to various data sources, the first findings date back to 4000 BC or 7000 BC. Boxing as a martial art began to be considered after it was included in the program of the ancient Olympic Games in 688 BC. Since boxing originated in ancient Greece, the first terms of boxing were reflected in the Greek-Latin language. "Pugilism" means "fist fight", meaning "boxing", and "Pugnus" means "fist" in Latin. It is worth noting that the word "pugil" has its Latin roots, and in English pugilist is a boxer, and pugilism is preserved in the meaning of "boxing" sport. Perhaps this is due to the fact that the Latin language is considered as a derivative of all Indo-European languages. Boxing (English boxing, box - from the word "hit") is one of the types of martial arts.

Key words: Roman Empire, terminological dictionary, English language, sport.

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The history of modern boxing is closely related to Great Britain. Boxing came to England with the arrival of the Roman Empire (Fleisher and Andre 1993). Modern boxing began there in the 18th century. In 1719, James Figg was recognized as the first heavyweight champion and is now recognized as the "Father of Boxing". This country is considered to be the country that developed and shaped the sport of boxing. The first written record of a boxing match dates back to 1681. Since the terminological dictionary of boxing has both terminological and international relations, this special language of boxing in English and Uzbek has a whole terminological commonality. In order to analyze and classify the terminological system of this sport in terms of derivation, various terms were considered, including lexical-semantic.

We can see morphological-syntactic terms and terminological acquisition of words. In the process of studying the terminological derivation of boxing, we come across various terms and lexemes. Examples of them are single-base terms, complex base terms, compound word terms and abbreviations (compound nouns).

The assimilation of boxing terms from English to Uzbek has a great impact on the development of the terminological system of the "boxing language" and, in general, each new neologism or borrowed word has a great impact on the development of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. The pronunciation of boxing terms is dominated by borrowing from the English language, that is, English words related to the field of boxing have spread to many countries that practice this sport, since the official language of this sport is English. In Uzbek boxing terminology, there are many words of English origin, because it is impossible to translate most of the English boxing terms into Uzbek and to find its alternatives, just like

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the sport of Uzbek National Wrestling. Because Uzbekistan is the homeland of the sport of wrestling, terms such as "kurash", "halal", "chala", "yonbosh" are widely spread to other countries that are engaged in the sport of wrestling, and boxing terms are used unchanged. For example: "swing" - "a side blow sent from a long distance", "uppercut" - "a blow sent from the lower side to the jaw, ring - boxing arena." We have mastered these words paying attention to English pronunciation and transcription. There is no alternative version of these words in Uzbek. Also, English word structure is unique. Words are formed in different ways. In English, some sports terms are affixed is formed. E.R. In her work, Medvedeva identifies the following most common affixes of sports lexemes:

1. Suffixes: -ing, -ed, -y ("cross-country skiing" - skiing, "dribbling" - beautiful movement in football, "safety car" - safety car, "lapped car" - circle car).

2. Prefixes: mis-, re-, un-, under - ("miskick" - an awkward kick to the ball in football, "restart" - restart (race), "unseated" - throw from a horse, "underarm" - in swimming a blow taken below body level).

Compound terms of six or more words:

pressing with the arm in the opponent's face" - pressing the opponent boxer's face with the hand. Boxing has enriched the English and Uzbek languages with bright expressions from the terminology of martial arts that have entered everyday life, in which we can give examples of various terms with figurative meaning:

- blow below the belt ("blow below the belt" - "blow below the belt", "forbidden blow");
- "to take it on the chin" - ("this is a boxing metaphor, don't shy away from the challenge");

- "be on the ropes" ("leaning on the ring ropes during the fight");

- "round" ("duration of boxing match" - "negotiation period");

- "to parry" ("to return a blow, defend oneself" - "to repel attacks quickly and skillfully", "to reject the opponent's arguments in a debate");

- "sparring" ("competition in training" - "dispute", "argument");

- "shadow fighting" = "shadow boxing", "infighting"

- "punch-drunken" ("to injure the head in the case of a blow" -> "to be surprised, surprised");

- "side-step" ("step to the side" -> "escape");

- "knock-out" ("knockout blow" - "unusual thing", "sensation", "great success").

Conclusion

In this chapter of the dissertation, boxing terminology and information about the emergence of boxing terms were given. Almost all terms of the sport of boxing are borrowed from English. We use some boxing terms we adopted it into our language in the form of appropriation and neologism. For example, we borrowed the words boxing, round and ring directly from the English language. Because there is no alternative version of these words in Uzbek.

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